

11-16 AUGUST 2019
22nd International Conference
on Composite Materials

Towards Self-Regulating Dental Composites

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Dental Restoration

Restoration requires binding between composite resins and dentin

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www.britannica.com

www.dentalimplantsthailand.org

- A composite resin restoration survives 5-7 years
- 50% of restorations placed by dentists replace existing restorations

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Debonding of Resin

Hydrolysis of exposed collagen over time by:

- Unpolymerized monomers
- Local enzymatic activities

Dentin-resin interface

Mortazavi et al., *Int. J. Dent.* (2012)

Biomodification of Dentin Collagens

- Intermolecular cross-links control the stability of collagen fibrils
- Polyphenol can enhance collagen cross-links

Tannic acid

Proanthocyanidins

Present in grape seed, pine nut and cinnamon bark extracts

In-Vitro Biomodification of Dentin

Treatment of demineralized dentin with aqueous solutions of cross-linkers for 4 hours

Bedran-Russo et al., *J. Biomed. Mater. Res., Part B* (2007)

Solution: Encapsulation of Extracts

- Protection from monomers
- Easier handling
- Sustained delivery

Dentin-resin interface

Materials System

- Core: Grape seed extract (GSE)
 - 95% proanthocyanidins
 - Water-soluble powder
- Shell polymer: Polylactide (PLA)
 - Biodegradable and biocompatible
 - Soluble in dichloromethane, chloroform, and tetrahydrofuran
- Resin system: Methacrylate-based
 - BIS-DMA: viscous monomer
 - TEG-DMA: low viscosity diluent monomer
 - CQ: visible-light initiator
 - EDAB: co-initiator

Water-in-Oil-in-Water Double Emulsion Technique

Step 1: W_i/O emulsion

W_i : GSE in DI water solution

O: PLA in dichloromethane (DCM)

Step 2: $(W_i/O)/W_o$ emulsion

Polynuclear Microcapsules

Morphology and size distribution

Microcapsules size histogram

Cross-section of microcapsules

Biomodification of Dentin Matrix

Aguiar et al., J. Dent. Res. (2014)

Yourdkhani et al., Dent. Mater. (2017)

Conclusions

- Successful encapsulation of natural extracts in PLA microcapsules for sustained bioactivity and long-term release
- Demonstrated sustained bioactivity of encapsulated core compounds after extraction from polymer microcapsules

Acknowledgments

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